

Experiencing FabLab without Boundaries: an Online Tool for Makers Community

Melike Mühür, Canberk Yurt

*Melike Mühür, İzmir Institute of Technology
İzmir, Turkey
melikemuhur@iyte.edu.tr*

*Canberk Yurt, İzmir Institute of Technology
İzmir, Turkey
canberkyurt@iyte.edu.tr*

Abstract

FabLabs are open and inclusive co-creation areas, by sharing not just tools and materials, but also knowledge, experiences and ideas. FabLab is not just a physical place, but also a meeting hub for makers, fabbers and any kind of participants to co-learn, collaborate and co-create. This mentality of FabLab has contributed to create the open and community-based maker culture of today. However, with the rise of virtual collaborative experiences and the appendage of Covid-19 Pandemic lockdowns and restrictions, the experience of FabLab has changed. This research aims to define the ways of recreating FabLabs' sharing and co-creation ecosystem in response to the dynamics of the online network era. Through the guidance of related concepts such as; open design, participatory design, culture of inclusion, human-computer interaction, etc. and the priorities of 3Cos as the fundamental aspects of FabLab, seven necessary principles for FabLab have been defined. These are phronesis, commons, distribution, entropy, emancipation, hedonia and reciprocity. By putting these seven principles at the centre, some common online platforms have been evaluated through Harris Profile method, so that the principles are explained in more depth and some statements and requirements have been reached for creating the suited online tool for FabLabs' community.

Keywords

FabLab, Co-creation, Makers, Digitalization, Online Social Network

1 Introduction

FabLabs are accessible makerspaces having a "common-based peer production approach" (Troxler & Wolf, 2010, p.2) which was developed based on the "How to do (almost) anything" lecture by Neil Gershenfeld (Gershenfeld, 2005). The number of FabLabs around the world has been recorded as 45 in 2010 (Troxler & Wolf, 2010) and 1003 in 2016 (Haldrup, et al. 2018). By 2021, according to the list in fablabs.io, it has reached 2030 labs worldwide and continues to increase.

Besides FabLab being one of the best representatives for the communal creation ecosystem, as a phenomenon, it is a social environment that facilitates knowledge sharing (Cabral & Winden, 2020), embraces non-expert users (Dreessen & Schepers, 2018) and serves the community wellbeing (Taylor, et al. 2016). The studies emphasizing FabLab as an open social space that goes beyond a production line consisting of mechanical tools have tried to explain it with the concept of third place, which has its origins in sociology (Dreessen & Schepers, 2018; Taylor, et al. 2016).

Third place is created by Oldenburg (1997) to set forth how functional that "third" social places separate from home or workplaces are among a society. According to Oldenburg (1997), third places meet the need for social interaction in a neighbourhood: they are informative, they provide solidarity, bring diverse people together to understand each other, and bring together those with similar interests enabling them to develop each other. These are such features that certainly can be associated with FabLab as well.

FabLab brings people from different professions together and facilitates the interaction between them. FabLab community strives to augment the maker society and to enable those who have been defined as users until today to participate in peer production and participatory practices. To create a widespread maker network, FabLab communities seek ways to engage the active participation of non-expert users. Therefore, third places with socially engaging benefits seem to be worth evaluating to create an inviting atmosphere for non-expert users (Dreessen & Schepers, 2018).

The rise of digital fabrication, in which 3d printers are the centre of attention, ends up with the “digital revolution” (Gershenfeld, 2005, p.7). Established as a physical space serving digital fabrication, FabLab has been managing to go beyond being an area of machines by combining the principles of free software, open-source and maker philosophies within. FabLab inevitably would have unique aspects while participating in the new digital transformation, too. Digitalization briefly depends on the technologically-induced changes (Gobble, 2018) that affect how humans transform their patterns of civilization from analogue to digital (Vogelsang, 2010), physical to virtual (Härting, et al. 2017).

Although, the physical place is a central part of a maker community, “online places for engaging in and talking about making are also a robust part of the maker movement” (Litts, et al. 2016, p.190). Digitalization is more than the emergence of technological advancements. It offers new platforms that enable self-representation and reaching self-esteem and self-actualization. The opportunity of participating and integrating a social group satisfies the humanistic need of being a part of a community. It is possible to interact and communicate through various digital mediums, generate reciprocal relations and gather participants who are sharing common social values (Echegaray, et al. 2021). For instance, social media platforms have changed our way of socializing (Obar & Wildman, 2015) and perceiving communal living in a physical world.

Digitalization has affected Maker society and the FabLab community, and their way of connecting, through digital transformation (Bounfour, 2016) and the formations of new interaction systems. Covid-19 Pandemic has accelerated this ongoing transition, as a result of some alterations caused by compulsory conditions and limitations. Distant work and education circumstances, lockdowns and restrictions, has affected the experience of FabLab, drastically. On the other hand, the pandemic era also witnessed examples of strong solidarity among the maker community. In the co-design practices conducted online, global collaborative actors had been able to meet and work together (Herrera, et al. 2021). Online crisis platforms organized or activated during this period such as C-19 Fablat (Herrera, et al. 2021) and Fab Safe Hub (Tsuda & Sakuragi, 2020) can be considered as the online projection of FabLab being an active actor in the practices.

However, while the online technologies and digital transformations are manipulating the existing patterns of living and general terms of interacting for various types of social groups across the World, some potentials are serving the hybrid nature of the FabLab community. To this end, through this research, some fundamental aspects and critical principles have been defined that are crucial for a special online tool that is dedicated to the FabLab community. For that, structured research has been made by following some complementary steps. By considering the unique values and the requirements of the FabLab community, the basic standards and the theoretical framework is defined.

1 FabLabs as centres of 3COs

It is time to expose FabLabs as centres of 3COs - co-learning, collaboration and co-creation - to create its active online projections. For understanding and then analyzing the three fundamental aspects of FabLabs some complementary and supportive concepts have been analyzed, to reinforce the statements that help to reach common values.

1.1 Co-Learning

Co-learning is the collective action of learning, which is the common activity of acquiring information to transform to knowledge, along the whole continuum. Learning is the process of gathering knowledge or changing behaviour (Armstrong, 2013). But the actual learning process is linked with the internalization of

practical knowledge in action (Weber & Khademian, 2008). Unlike the individual learning process, co-learning functions through active social interactions, participatory practices, and personal contributions to the knowledge generation processes (Webb, 2009). Co-learning generates common knowledge that is gained through action, reflection and experimentation. Besides, it aims to build a common-accepted basis by experiencing the process of solving complexities. At this point, unlike conventional knowledge creation and learning processes, co-learning highlights the importance of another virtue; Aristotelian phronesis (Armstrong, 2013), adding to the commonly accepted virtues; *techne* and *episteme* (Aristotle, et al. 2009).

Because of being a collective, collaborative, iterative and self-feeding learning mechanism, co-learning is the intrinsically compatible model of sharing knowledge and skills for the FabLab case. Because of following the principles of open design, the spirit of experimentation, generating alternative solutions through models like forking and RepRap, co-learning suits the FabLab dynamics and Maker culture. Similarly, failure is one of the most effective learning experiences as a common value both for FabLabs and co-learning.

1.2 Collaboration

Collaboration is the collective working of a group of people or organizations to complete a task or achieve a goal (Martinez-Moyano, 2006). It is a social activity that gathers communities for optimizing the use of limited resources and efforts, on the contrary to a system of competition and rivalry (Leydesdorff & Wagner, 2009), towards the common target. Through this collaborative environment in society, the representatives of commons will be triggered to discover, innovate and negotiate new ways of doing things (Bollier & Helfrich, 2014), by operating social relationships and shared knowledge (Macrae, 2017). Through co-experiencing, these communal activities (Fuchs & Obrist, 2010) both social (Surman, 2013) and collaborative innovation (Capdevila, 2015) will be achieved. In the inclusive and intersubjective community formation and the collaborative, open, democratic and collective value creation processes (Fuchs & Obrist, 2010), members are willing to express themselves by their knowledge, wills, and creativity (Banathy, 1996) and contribute through personally meaningful activities (Fischer & Giaccardi, 2006).

With digitalization, the activities have shifted from primitive expert-oriented to a more open collaboration-oriented structure. Through that, the bottom-up, reciprocal and bidirectional participant involvement have been boosted. New value creation processes depend on openness and effective knowledge sharing, through cross-disciplinary structures and collaboration (Osunyomi, 2016). Third places and creative hubs (Virani & Malem, 2015, Dovey, et al. 2016) and cultural and creative collaborative spaces (Tomaz, 2019), such as; makerspaces, hackerspaces and FabLabs are based on practice rather than passive reproduction of knowledge (Wolf et al., 2020). In this collaborative environment, the main concern is to experience collaboration and cooperation, without feeling the pressure of profit, efficiency and competitiveness (Kostakis, et al. 2015) through peer production (Nascimento, 2014) with people from various backgrounds and with diverse skills (Sennett, 2012).

1.3 Co-Creation

As a part of a community, persons are willing to experience intellectual, social and hedonic benefits of sharing (Nambisan & Baron, 2009). Creative activities enable common experiences through social engagement and cultural accumulation. Plus, creation is more than the process of creating things or systems. It is also a hermeneutic activity that ends up with interpreting to premises and meaning-making. Meaning can just be generated by absolute co-creation (Ind & Coates, 2013). It is the process of creation through the absolute interpretation of the skills and cultural reflections (Leavy, 2012). So far, co-creation is widening through online tools, a transition from product-based to service-based economy, openness in innovation and enhancement of social interaction, collaboration and customization trends (Ind & Coates, 2013).

Co-creation is a crucial vision for makers, by enhancing the sense of being part of a community (Koh & Kim, 2003). Co-creation directly links with the collective atmosphere of FabLabs and the makers community, by saturating the experience of experimenting together and reaching practical questioning as a social group. By focusing on the process rather than the outcome and being freedom-centric (Ramaswamy & Ozcan, 2020) prototyping-dependent and experience-oriented (Ind & Coates, 2013), co-

creation is a practical tool for the FabLab atmosphere. Also, FabLabs can integrate non-professional participants and influential groups into the collective creation process of social innovation. As a result of that, open-source and community-driven innovations can be accepted and widened, just like Linux or Wikipedia (Raymond, 1999). It is a democratic way of generating knowledge agreed among communities through commoning (Gauditz & Euler, 2017).

2 Methodology

For determining the principles under 3CO aspects of FabLab and structuring the outlines of the online third place for FabLab community, some structured research has to be made. The predominant methodological approach of this research is Phenomenology, as a result of generating ideas and making analysis through the experiences about some phenomenological aspects of FabLabs and the Maker culture. To reach the overview of the online formation of the FabLab community, the recent platforms and concepts have been evaluated through the critical analysis approach, from the point of view of Maker glasses.

The research consists of two main steps. In the first step, through the combination of the insights from literature surveys of the related concepts and evaluation of the characteristics of FabLab and Maker culture, the principles of the online tool are defined. For generating tangible improvements, some secondary research has been made. By evaluating the current performance of some selected online platforms and Fab Network with the principles of the online FabLab tool, through the Harris Profile method, some insights have been gathered. The assessments in this section provided an opportunity to better explain the principles as well. In the discussion part, all the outcomes of this research have been synthesized for the conclusion.

2.1 Critical Analysis of the Related Concepts

For defining the principles for the online tool, some related concepts have been analyzed. The critical analysis has been made by concentrating on the priorities of particular concept definitions in the literature. With the literature survey of usability, collaboration, participatory design, co-creation, open-source design, inclusive design, diversity, human-computer interaction and some other related concepts, common and crucial principles have been listed, comparatively. To analyze them in a bigger picture, the common elements of these concepts are highlighted (Table 1).

According to Table 1, there are some common and unique prioritized values in each particular concept, according to their focuses and tendencies. The common elements are the potential inspiration for our proposal, because being important among various concepts. However, because of aiming to create a platform that is specific for FabLab and the Maker culture, there is a need to re-evaluate these values critically, by putting the priorities and tenets of the Maker community at the centre. For instance, as mentioned repeatedly, especially in the UI/UX, usability, human-computer interaction literature, the principles like efficiency, comprehensibility (Bhaskar, et al. 2011), effectiveness, error-tolerant (Quesenbery, 2004), productivity (Alnanih & Ormandjieva, 2016), pragmatic (Nambisan & Nambisan, 2008; Kohler, et al. 2011), etc. are controversial with the dynamics of the FabLab. As offering an alternative approach for producing and making, maker and FabLab cultures stand for the importance of phronesis, the trial and error and the magic of the opportunities by randomness. That is why, more than a result-oriented mentality, FabLabs are the ecosystems for casual experiences. Besides, the over-spoken principles like, freedom, feedback, error safety (McCracken & Wolfe, 2004), accessibility (Galitz, 2007), usability (Komninos, 2020), etc. are causing devaluation, because of leading shallow and stereotypical discussions.

Also, some inherently linking values are suitable to the dynamics of the FabLab. For instance, the hedonic aspect (Nambisan & Nambisan, 2008; Kohler, et al. 2011), directly bonds with the experience of the maker culture, through the enjoyment of the making by experimentation. Plus, the social cohesion by co-creation activities is the supportive element for the hedonic values of the FabLab experience. Reciprocal understanding (Pless & Maak, 2004) is also a directly fitting value for the FabLab culture, by supporting the importance of dialogue and inclusiveness in the FabLab ecosystem.

Related Concepts	a	Human Computer Interaction (McCracken & Wolfe, 2004), (Fuchs & Obrist, 2010), (Alnanih & Ormandjieva, 2016)			
	b	Usability (Quesenberg, 2004), (Shneiderman, 1997) (Dey, 2010), (Nielsen 2012), (Komninos, 2020), (Wong 2020)			
	c	UI/UX (Galitz, 1992; 2007), (Mosier & Smith, 1995), (Bhaskar et al. 2011), (Nielsen & Norman, 2020)			
	d	Culture of Inclusion (Iannello, 1992), (Dempsey, 2001), (Pless & Maak, 2004), (Simmons-Mackie & Damico, 2007)			
	e	Participatory Design (Schuler & Namioka, 1993), (Grønbaech et al., 1997), (Kensing & Blomberg, 1998), (Gregory, 2003)			
	f	Co-Creation (Nambisan & Nambisan, 2008), (Kohler et al. 2011), (Blaschke et al., 2019), (Ramaswamy & Ozcan, 2020)			
	g	Collaboration & Co-Learning (Surman, 2013), (Navarro-García et al., 2015), (Vasilchenko et al., 2020)			
	h	Open source & Open design (Stallman, 2009), (Pomerantz & Peek, 2016), (Creative Commons, 2021)			
Principles	Literature	Principles	Literature	Principles	Literature
Openness	a, h	Familiarity	c	Generativity	f
Participatory	a, e, h	Flexibility	c, g	Linkability	f
Community	a, e, g	Forgiveness	c	Evolvability	f
Efficiency	a, b, c	Immersion	c, f	Ecosystem-oriented	f
Freedom	a, e, f, h	Operability	c	Technology-oriented	f
User Capacity	a	Perceptibility	c	Mobilization-oriented	f
Affordance	a	Positive Impression	c	Interaction-oriented	f
Visibility	a	Predictability	c	Commitment	g
Feedback	a, b, c	Transparency	c, f, g, h	Curation	g
Metaphor	a	Trade-Offs	c	Connection	g
Productivity	a	Social construction	d, e	Culture	g
Effectiveness	a, b,	Negotiation	d, e	Cross-disciplinary	g
Error Safety	a, b, c	Manifestation	d	Awareness raising	g
Engaging	b	Collaboration	d, f	Creative Commons	h
Easy to Learn	b, c	Reciprocity	e	Free	h
Consistency	b, c	Democracy	e	Copyleft	h
Enable shortcuts	b	Imagined Futures	e	Peer-to-peer	h
Dialogue	b, e, f	Conflicting	e	Mass-collaboration	h
Control	b, c	Pragmatic	f	Sharing	h
Accessibility	c, f, g, h	Sociability	f	Forking	h
Aesthetic	c	Usability	b, f, h	Rights	h
Availability	c	Hedonic	f	Distributable	h
Clarity	c	Creativity	f	Remixable	h
Compatibility	c	Transformativity	f	Adaptable	h
Comprehensibility	c	Reflexivity	f	Activism	h
Directness	c	Inclusivity	f		

Table 1: The list of the principles from the literature survey of related concepts.

Through the combination of gatherings from literature and the characteristics of FabLab culture, the relevant and convenient framework is defined for the general principles of FabLab and the online tool for expanding its boundaries.

3 Principles for the Online Tool

The seven principles are defined as requirements for the online tool that specifically functions as a community hub for the participants of the FabLab ecosystem. The unique characteristics and dynamics of FabLab culture are guaranteed through these seven principles along with the transformation from the physical environment to a digital platform.

3.1 Phronesis

Phronesis is the ethical and critical judgement process for making deliberation about values regarding praxis. It is pragmatic, variable, context-dependent and oriented toward action (Flyvbjerg, 2001). Phronesis is wisdom by practical action to reach a practical judgement. It enables questioning, monitoring and evaluating. It is the premise of the learning by doing approach. It triggers the exact way of questioning through inquiry and reasoning (Aristotle, et al. 2009). Phronesis is a stance for common understanding and authority (Armstrong, 2013). As a result that, it enables us to dream about the possibilities and make speculations about the future. So, it is possible to be fictitious and creative by breaking the stereotyping mentalities. That is why having phronesis is crucial for the FabLab ecosystem for constructing fictional futures.

3.2 Commons

The concept of commons is the social practice of shared resources, ideals, knowledge and motivations without any ownership or privilege among any members of the community (Ostrom, et al. 1999). The new ways of acting together (Gauditz & Euler, 2017) and defining original dynamics for the shared values creates the commons (De Angelis, 2010). FabLabs provide the exact environment for commoning through the commons-based peer production mentality (Benkler, 2006). They are contributing to the Creative Commons, by supporting openness (Lessig, 2004) and standing against the restrictive permission culture dominated by monopolies (Lessig, 2003). Plus, FabLabs are kind of third places which are functioning as sorting areas by promoting the habit of association among the members who are sharing special interests (Oldenburg, 1997). They serve as social spaces that support wellbeing, answering the dynamics of local communities and reaching the marginal groups (Taylor, et al. 2016). As a result that, any medium of FabLab must be designed in the consideration of local commons and have to function as a commoning agency of the community.

3.3 Distribution

Sharing multiple types of resources (Pomerantz & Peek, 2016), such as; knowledge, equipment, and experience, is one of the fundamental dynamics of the FabLab ecosystem. Distribution of all assets and capital without any economic ambitions creates the unique spirit of co-creation, collaboration and co-learning activities. It is also crucial for open design and open platforms. Through forking movements (Pomerantz & Peek, 2016) and with the help of some digital advancements, open designs are being developed by any participant across the world. Distribution also enables sharing the workload and spending resources, logically. To this end, for creating an open, fair, free and active FabLab ecosystem, the distribution of resources and expertise is necessary. So, the FabLab ecosystem has to function as a meeting hub that directs and connects various users and platforms. For the digital case, the global FabLab platform can be the absolute distribution network by linking related organizations, online platforms and communities, rather than dominating, manipulating or prioritizing any smaller entities in the ecosystem.

3.4 Entropy

Maker culture embraces unmaking as well as making; which connotes "chance" and "entropy" (Song & Paulos, 2021). Entropy as a principle means not having a predictable order and emphasizes being casual and inefficient. Inefficiency, in this sense, indicates a stance against result-oriented working which leads to unsustainable progress. Inefficiency is a core element to create an active community spending long hours together and having a chance "to learn by trial and error, to inspire each other, exchange ideas and experiences" (Haldrup, et al. 2018, p.3). Entropy provides a complicated order that looks like chaos on the surface and explains the fluid interaction within the maker community. Rather than a workshop, Fablab is

defined as a constant experiment that brings people together and waits to see what happens through endless possibilities (Haldrup, et al. 2018).

3.5 Emancipation

Emancipation as a principle means an opening towards diversity, not just freedom. It is not a static word; it indicates a community is always becoming. The concept of imperfection which means "a new take on old ideas" (Sudjic, 2014) can be useful in explaining this principle. Perfection as the opposite concept is a value of mass production age that is required by industrial production and moulding technologies at the expense of eliminating differences (Sudjic, 2014). However, the digital age of 3d printing has heralded that imperfection has turned into a sought-after value. Online tools that allow anonymous identities provide examples of the emancipatory experience. Besides, the limited stereotypes that internet providers define for users pose a threat in allowing diversity. For reaching true potential of emancipation, anonymity must be established in a flexible structure. This refers to a fiction in which users are not obliged to a single persona in the online network they are involved in. Another important issue here is that "persona" should not be confused with stereotypes. Persona should be treated as a method based on a user-centred approach (Marsden & Haag, 2016), existing stereotypes should not create bias while understanding the characteristics of potential users. Furthermore, it would be emancipatory to allow users to create different personas and to role-playing, as a flexible feature provided by the online environment.

3.6 Hedonia

One of the most characteristic aspects of FabLab is to offer an enjoyable experience. The experimental nature of making creates a socially satisfying co-creation atmosphere in FabLabs. The hedonic needs are being covered through various ways along with experimenting. Through the collective participation in FabLabs, the pleasure of sharing intellectual and social values provides hedonic satisfaction (Nambisan & Baron, 2009). From Nozick's point of view, just making a difference and speculating the existence is the way to reach hedonia (Nozick, 1974). Also, from a more Kantian perspective, creating things or experiencing the process of creating gives an aesthetic pleasure through the harmonious togetherness of understanding and imagination (De Clercq, 2019). In any way, hedonic point of view (Nambisan & Nambisan, 2008), is crucial requirement, both in the physical and virtual medium of FabLab (Kohler, et al. 2011).

3.7 Reciprocity

Reciprocity is crucial for ensuring the inviting, democratic and non-hierarchical FabLab experience. Through breaking authority for co-learning, enabling different voices for unique co-creation and making social cohesion with collaboration, the reciprocal relations are about to be covered in maker communities. Because of having an interaction-oriented ecosystem (Blaschke, et al. 2019), FabLabs have to ensure the value creation processes operated through the involvement of more than one brain. Peer-to-peer interactions generate free flow reciprocal logic (Bianchini, et al. 2018) and the development of open-source movement (Benkler, 2003). Dialogue-driven co-learning, collaboration and co-creation processes (Ramaswamy & Ozcan, 2020) trigger the participants' involvement (Grønbaech, et al. 1997). As a result that, it is possible to spread the culture of inclusion by ensuring reciprocal understanding among the community members (Pless & Maak, 2004).

4 Evaluation of the Selected Online Platforms

4.1 Selection of the Case Platforms

After laying out the principles specialized for the maker community of FabLab, we conduct a review of existing online tools to understand how to interpret these principles. For that, we firstly conducted a broad search for the current online tools, then revealed some headings according to functions or methods of the platforms. These headings have been narrowed down to 7 main categories: (MOOCs) Massive open online

courses, Cloud storage, Developer platforms, Visual collaboration platforms for teams, VOIP communication systems for online gaming, Social networking and Portfolio platforms (Table 2).

CATEGORY	WHAT THEY OFFER	EXPLANATION	SELECTED PLATFORMS	SELECTION REASONS
1. MOOCs	Co-learning; Accessible information	The most popular MOOC platforms are listed as: Udemy, Coursera, EdX, Udacity, MiriadaX, UNED COMA, Futurelearn, Open Learning and NovoEd (Martin, et al. 2016; Chaw & Tang, 2019).	UDEMY (udemy.com)	It is one of the most popular platforms that is suitable to represent its category.
2. Cloud Storage Platforms	Archiving and transferring the knowledge	Major cloud storage services which are used to store and share data online are listed as: Dropbox, Google Drive, Microsoft Onedrive (Chu, et al. 2013; Li, et al. 2014).	GOOGLE DRIVE (drive.google.com)	Moreover, it is the most familiar one to the researchers.
3. Developer Platforms	Co-creation; Gathering the experts & non-experts together	Github is mentioned as the largest social developer platform hosting millions of software projects (Borges & Valente, 2018). StackOverflow is a Q&A platform used with Github which succeeded in gamification by allowing its users to vote questions and answers and encourage them to contribute more (Vasilescu, et al. 2013).	STACKOVERFLOW (stackoverflow.com) & GITHUB (github.com)	Two significant platforms having interplay with each other for developers.
4. Visual Collaboration	Co-working, remote working with a team; Workshop tools	These are separated from the other online tools with the visual elements they offer. Adapting the design thinking tools in a creative way for remote working, providing digital workflows and digital whiteboards that enable interaction can be listed as the main features that make them special.	MIRO (miro.com)	It is the most familiar one to the researchers.
5. VOIP Communication for Online Gaming	Chat; Hedonic experience	Discord is a new generation chat platform, especially used for gaming, but also as a communication tool for teams in the purpose of working (Gama et. al., 2021)	DISCORD (discord.com)	It is one of the most popular communication platforms for online gaming.
6. Social Networking	Socializing; Expressing yourself; Knowledge acquisition	Sourtimes (eksisozluk.com) is "the largest Turkish online social network" (Kuzu & Salah, 2018). Sourtimes, which is organized as informative pages that authors create, provides communication between authors mainly through messaging. On the other hand, in accordance with various needs, it has been strengthened by side elements such as a forum-type platform organized in the form of questions and answers (eksiduyuru.com). Unlike Reddit (Overdorf & Greenstadt, 2016) which can be considered as a similar platform for some aspects, Sourtimes does not allow users to have multiple accounts.	SOURTIMES (EKSIISOZLUK) (eksisozluk.com)	Largest online platform in Turkey for years and suitable to represent social networking culture with its forum-like side platform.
7. Portfolio Platforms	Expressing yourself; Earning reputation; Getting inspiration	Portfolio platforms are useful online tools for individuals to share their knowledge and projects and to get inspiration. This category is mainly included here since these platforms offer an aesthetically satisfying style to display projects.	DRIBBBLE (dribbble.com)	It is a popular platform that researchers are familiar with.

Table 2: Selection of online tools for principle analysis.

Then, platforms have selected and listed for each category. To make an appropriate selection, the relevant literature was reviewed and it was strived to ensure that the platform was capable of representing the function the category announces. In addition, the familiarity of platforms to the researchers has been considered as another selection criteria. The reason for studying on individual platforms instead of a general evaluation for the categories is that the online platforms mentioned have separate characteristics and cannot be evaluated together. It is believed that, the comparison between selected platforms would help to materialize how the principles work for the online tools.

4.2 Harris Profile Analysis

At this stage, which aims to clarify the principles through the selected platforms, Harris profile is applied as a comparative visual method. Harris Profile or New Product Profile is a comparison and decision making tool to evaluate especially conceptual alternatives according to criteria defined in a hierarchy. It is used as a design thinking method in design processes to visualize the strengths and weaknesses of the product alternatives (van Boeijen, et al. 2013).

In our study, despite not comparing new product concepts, we have two reasons for selecting Harris Profile as the evaluation method:

1. The hierarchy between our principles directly fits with the hierarchical arrangement criteria in Harris Profile.
2. The complex results of the comparison of diverse platforms can be solved through the Harris Profile’s unique visualization performance.

Our 7 principles were placed together with the 8 selected platforms and Fab Network, which is a premise for the makers' online tool, as in the table and voted together by two researchers of this study coming from the design discipline. The principles are placed in order of importance from top to bottom. Inferences about platforms are based on mainly subjective experiences. The aim here is to make the principles derived from the research understandable through the available online tools (Figure 1).

	UDEMY				GOOGLE DRIVE				STACKOVERFLOW				GITHUB				MIRO				DISCORD				SOURTIMES				DRIBBBLE				FAB NETWORK							
	-2	-1	1	2	-2	-1	1	2	-2	-1	1	2	-2	-1	1	2	-2	-1	1	2	-2	-1	1	2	-2	-1	1	2	-2	-1	1	2	-2	-1	1	2				
PHRONESIS			1								1				1												1													
COMMONS																																								
DISTRIBUTION																																								
ENTROPY																																								
EMANCIPATION																																								
HEDONIA																																								
RECIPROCITY																																								

Figure 1: Harris Profile Analysis.

4.3 Evaluation and Discussion

In this study, the platforms that are popular and successful examples of its category, negative votes in the evaluations generally indicate irrelevance or lack compared to other platforms, not a failure. Since the study is done to demonstrate which platform stands out for each principle, the platforms are compared according to their claims and weighted usage purposes. The Harris profile is normally an evaluation for the selection of the best alternative, and the top criteria on the table matter more for the selection to be made. While implementing the Harris Profile, we determined a hierarchy for the principles and placed them accordingly. However, when interpreting the results, we did not consider to choose the best. So we utilized Harris Profile method as a data visualization tool to demonstrate which platform’s structure offers more for each principle.

Phronesis, as a primary principle for the FabLab ecosystem, was evaluated through the consideration of experimental participation and practical wisdom. Because of offering free intervention by forking and gathering the interested groups, GitHub covers the dynamics of phronesis. Udemy, Google Drive, Miro, Dribbble also embrace the phronesis through co-learning and co-creation processes, but there is a slight hierarchy between users, and the concentration to this principle is not as powerful as in GitHub. On the other hand, in Fab Network, the groups and topics are for gathering people and making them communicate for their future works. Fab Network is not a suitable platform for the regeneration of experienced and agreed knowledge by applying the dynamics of phronesis.

Commons is taken as a requirement for creating a united community for the same targets. Stackoverflow and Discord fulfil this principle, by primarily focusing on bringing people together in specified groups and channels. Through commoning, social interaction and finding common subtopics are being achieved by the free intervention of each user. Moreover, Fab Network takes it a step further, by already addressing a specified group of people consisting of FabLab community members. Fab Network also hosts some sub-

groups that are concentrated on some special topics and working areas. On the other hand, Google Drive and even Miro are far away from absolute commoning, because both of them function through the preferences of authorized users of the folder, document or whiteboard, by limiting the free access and participation of anonymous users.

Distribution principle is an irreplaceable element of the open-source development model. Considering distribution, Udemy and Github achieved the highest scores. It is not a surprising result for these two platforms aimed at organizing distributive learning and development models. On the other hand, Google Drive, Miro and Discord platforms gained negative scores. Since they do not seem to centre the distributive development model as much as others. Although they allow for collaborative work, they seem to lead them to more introverted, disjointed groups.

When it comes to the entropy principle, all platforms except Sourtimes and Discord received negative votes. Entropy is the expression of a system that does not tolerate predetermined organizations, planning, profit motive and efficiency. Accordingly, rule-based and result-oriented platforms that do not centre inefficiency will not reference open-ended relationships that FabLab requires. The reason why Sourtimes gets the highest rank is, its horizontally interconnected layout becomes unpredictable with parallel pages, and this world can expand noticeably with individual contributions. It is anticipated that within the framework of the entropy principle of the online tool to be developed for FabLab, it will benefit from the horizontally and vertically linked but not limited structure of the Sourtimes platform. Moreover, Sourtimes succeeds in creating a sense of timelessness, since it allows a random circulation as well as a comprehensive searching skill and long-term communication.

Emancipation principle means unlocking the possibilities brought by the online revolution to ensure diversity. Personas, which are shaped according to interactions in the physical world, gain the freedom to take on an ambiguous and variable character at any time when they are moved to the online universe. For this principle, none of the platforms met the expectations very well and could not receive +2 points. Some platforms were able to get +1 points since they allow you to create a unique identity and avatar online. On the other hand, Udemy and Dribbble received negative points as it was thought that they did not provide the desired feeling of freedom as they encouraged to their singular point of view.

The fulfilment of hedonia has been evaluated by considering the enjoyment, interaction, self-representation and perpetuity along with the experiences. Because of being the most accepted representative online platforms in their categories, each one performs well from the hedonic perspective. However, when we dig deep, there are some nuances among these platforms. As a result of having better interfaces and more fluent circulations, Dribbble, Stackoverflow and Discord fulfils the hedonia. On the other hand, because of offering the same kind of experiences, stereotyped interaction levels and standardized processes, Google Drive, Miro, Udemy and Github offer limited hedonic satisfaction. Fab Network has also got a monotonous and unsurprising experience, because of offering just announcements and forum conversations. As a response to these problems, Sourtimes offers unexpected experiences each time of use, through spontaneous and reflexive surfing from one page to another.

Reciprocity is a crucial feature of social networking platforms. While platforms generally get high scores for this principle in the table, Stackoverflow stands out with its effort to increase interaction and gamification with scoring in the question and answer section. Miro as an effective tool for live collaboration, and Discord with its non-hierarchical structure in communication, are candidates to be inspiring for this principle.

As a premise online platform, Fab Network achieved its highest scores from commons, emancipation, hedonia and reciprocity principles. However, it is evaluated as a weak platform for phronesis, distribution and entropy principles. To create an ideally harmonious online tool for the FabLab community, some modifications have to be made. First of all, for a functional environment for obtaining phronesis, the integration of versatile multimedia tools is crucial. Diverse possibilities of intervention to the platform enable free, flexible, unexpected and unique contributions for reaching practical and agreed knowledge. It will also increase hedonic satisfaction by offering dynamic experiences. Second, for creating a distributive atmosphere and obtaining democratic sharing of the resources and respectful contribution to the open community, adding a subcategory that functions as a bridge between the related platforms and

the community will be beneficial. Third, for answering the entropy principle, the structure of the platform must be designed non-hierarchically and prioritized. Because of performing like a parent organization, The Fab Foundation created weight on the entropy. Also, the menus and groups are target-oriented rather than being experimental or inefficient. By providing a more unplanned and spontaneous experience the entropy principle can be achieved. With all these modifications, the ultimate FabLab experience will be maintained in the online tool for the makers' community.

5 Conclusion

As a result of this study, 3Cos (collaboration, co-creation and co-learning) of FabLab were revealed by an in-depth literature review and 7 unique principles to sustain an online community for FabLab were determined; phronesis, commons, distribution, entropy, emancipation, hedonia and reciprocity. By considering the existing performances and experiences of some selected common platforms and Fab Network, some inferences have been reached. In the light of these results, designing, building and developing this online tool for FabLab community can be considered as a further study. Also, the physical and virtual experience of the FabLab and the reciprocal impacts of these experiences on themselves could be considered as a research case for further studies.

Acknowledgement

There is no conflict of interest to disclose.

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